

Quantum Wave / Particle Duality and Time and Space

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In classical physics and even for classical mechanical waves, one follows an object (or wave crest) in time and space, i.e. time and space are coupled through a velocity. In some quantum situations, there is also a similar classical notion of time and space. For example, a photon or electron source is located at a point x and emits a photon/electron at a certain time. These travel with a fixed velocity (momentum is known exactly) to a detector at a specific x position where they are registered at a specific time t .

If one examines a bound state, however, time only appears in $\exp(-iEt)$. One has a spatial problem with no clear momentum at x i.e. $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ (a complex conditional probability). A statistical resonance occurs which creates humps in space, but these are due to interference of $\exp(ipx)$ conditional probability waves which, we argue, are based on invariance throughout space.

In this note, we try to argue that the quantum wavefunction approach maps a physical problem into a continuum (spatially invariant) picture where the wave $\exp(ipx)$ exists for all x . One may, however, have degeneracy in a continuum system. For example, mechanical waves in a continuum may be created at different origins. Two such waves could be out of phase due to this degeneracy. The same degeneracy exists in quantum mechanics, with different origins leading to different phases. Given a phase in $\exp(ipx + i \text{ phase})$, however, one does not know for certain whether the phase is due to different origins. It could be due to a Bohm-Aharonov effect, so space does not enter into the problem except through the $\exp(ipx)$ cycle and the resulting interference.

Classical Physics and Time and Space

In classical physics and also mechanical waves, one may deterministically follow an object (particle or crest of a wave) in time and space. Both the particle and wave crest may be measured at any x and time (in the trajectory). In some quantum situations, a similar scenario seems to hold on the surface. One has a source of photons or electrons at a specific x emitting say an electron at a given time t . The electron moves with an exactly known momentum p and arrives at a detector at a specific x at a specific time where its momentum is measured. (E.g. an electron or photon strikes a piece of foil.). This appears as a completely classical scenario, yet in quantum mechanics it is argued that a free electron is described by a wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ which holds at all x . This is already strange because the source of the electron exists at a specific x_1 . One could try to create a step function and argue that the wavefunction is zero to the left of the source and $\exp(ipx)$ to the right, but this implies it is a superposition of many different $\exp(ikx)$ which does not seem that that is the case when the electron hits the foil. Alternatively (and traditionally), the electron is described by a wavepacket, i.e. a superposition of $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ waves, but a Gaussian form at t_1 will spread in time to having a larger and larger variance which seems unphysical.

Quantum Mechanics and Invariance

We argue that the conditional probability $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ for an electron or photon is based on invariance. A wave equation $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} W - \frac{1}{cc} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W = 0$ allows for W to be separable i.e. $W(x)W(t)$, with each piece behaving in a periodic manner i.e. $\exp(ipx-iEt)$. Such a wave equation appears if there seems to be invariance (sometimes only in a region as in the case of a string tied at both ends), but the scenario should also lead to derivatives d/dx and d/dt (partial). In the case of a wave on a string, a wave equation appears which holds in all of space. Forcing boundary conditions brings the physical endpoints into the picture. Thus, we argue that a wave exists in all of space and time, is based on invariance and represents decoupling of time and space.

For a relativistic quantum particle, we have argued in previous notes that one may vary the classical action for a constant velocity $= x/t$ independently in terms of x and t . Classically, this should not be done because x and t are not independent, but one finds:

$$\text{Action} = \int dt L = -t m_0 \sqrt{1-vv} \quad \text{with } d\text{Action}/dt = -E \text{ and } d\text{Action}/dx = p \quad ((1))$$

Then $\exp(i \text{Action})$ satisfies a wave equation.

In this note, we argue that even though there exists invariance throughout all space for a wave, there may also be degeneracies. For example, one wave may have one origin and another another origin i.e. $\exp(i px_1)$ versus $\exp(i p x_2)$. These two waves may be out of phase and interfere. Thus, the idea of different spatial locations of the sources of two electrons both with momentum p exists, but is converted into phases. At a detector, one cannot prove that the different phases are due to different origins. They might be due to the Bohm-Aharonov effect, i.e. a potential which does not change the magnitude of p in one dimension. Although the sources exist at two points x_1 and x_2 and the detector is at another point x_3 , one does not deal explicitly with distances in a classical way. Distance enters through the behaviour of the wavelength cycle and interference. Thus, even though one uses $\exp(ipx)$ which holds for all x , the physical problem may occur in a subset of space from x_1 to x_3 . There seems to be a mapping occurring from a finite region to an infinite one. This also holds for say a bound oscillator. The classical turning points may be roughly viewed in a wavefunction solution, with the wavefunction dying down to zero away from these points.

In a bound system, one uses $\exp(ipx)$ which holds in all of space, but imposes boundary conditions to roughly have the system restricted to a region of space. In the case of a box with infinite walls, the spatial boundaries are strict and the wavefunction is zero exactly at the walls and outside, but $\exp(ipx)$'s are still used which exist throughout all of space to create an $\exp(ipx)$ within the box. They then interfere outside the box to create a zero wavefunction. Thus, the notion of full invariance still exists with $\exp(ipx)$'s even for a box with infinite walls.

Invariance in the Case of a Photon

A wave equation for either the electric or magnetic field (or $E+iB$) may be obtained from Maxwell's equations by removing charge and current sources which normally govern the E and B fields. This leads to $\partial B/\partial t = -\text{grad} \times E$ and $\partial E/\partial t = \text{grad} \times B$. There are derivatives in these equations, but nothing governing motion in x or t i.e. there is invariance in these two dimensions, but also derivatives. This leads to a wave solution $\exp(ipx - iEt)$.

It is known, however, that an accelerating charge radiates. For example, the charge may be subject to an undulating field as in a synchrotron. One may calculate the electric and magnetic fields at a specific point x,t . How is this linked to the invariant wave solution? For an invariant wave solution there is a degeneracy. One may have different origins. These lead to phase shifts i.e. $\exp(ipx_1)$ versus $\exp(ipx_2)$ which have physical consequences i.e. incoherent light. If one may have electron bunching in a synchrotron, i.e. electrons being very close to each other, then there is a greater chance for coherence i.e. no degeneracy. (1) Thus, the idea of different creation space points is important for photons too, but again leads to phase shifts.

Two Slit Experiment

A free photon is described by a wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$, but as it moves through space it seems to be classical i.e. its momentum is exactly known. One may ask then: What does $\exp(ipx)$ mean? We argue that this is complex because it is not considered as the electron moves freely through space, but is manifest through certain potentials e.g. a magnetic vector potential A , a bound state potential or a two slit potential to give a few examples. We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability and so a kind of statistical resonance or equilibrium is formed. The electron, described by $\exp(ipx)$, forms a resonance with the two-slit potential leading to the possibility for the electron to go off at non-classical angles with different weights. If a detector is placed behind each slit to determine whether the electron passes through one or the other, the interference pattern is destroyed. The detector "breaks" statistical resonance or equilibrium and the electron goes back to being a "particle" again. If it encounters another two slit type potential, however, it may create a resonance again.

For a bound state, the wavefunction $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. A resonance is created by $\exp(ipx)$ probability waves interacting with $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$. This leads to a spatial wave pattern. If one knocks the quantum single particle out of its bound state, it will be detected with one of the p values and appear as a particle. Given an ensemble of such states, one finds a momentum distribution of $a(p)a(p)$. The "particle" picture of the particle gives partial information about the wave picture. One would need to be aware that the square root of $a(p)a(p)$ is needed (there is still the issue of sign even if $a(p)$ is real) and create $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Thus, it seems that one may have more than simply particle and wave pictures. One may have a combination of both if one uses ensembles, for example.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that wave physics is based on decoupling of time and space and on invariance arguments. This invariance exists even for classical waves like water waves, sound

waves and waves on a string. Classically, one tries to follow a crest of a wave which has a specific velocity and so turns the wave (or at least its crest) into a classical object detectable at each x at a certain time. For quantum mechanics, we argue that one does do this. For example, $\exp(-iEt)$ simply means there is an overall energy of E in a bound state. T and x are decoupled. As a result, wave packets, which spread out over time, also do not need to be used, we argue.

We suggest that quantum mechanics involves mapping a finite space problem into an invariant system which exists over all space. This holds even for a particle in a finite length box with an infinite potential at the walls (or other bound problems) and for particles created at different origins. How does one handle the latter? We argue that one may have degenerate invariant solutions i.e. $\exp(ipx_1)$ and $\exp(ipx_2)$ which map to quantum objects created at different origins. This leads to different phases and a different interference pattern, but does not involve following a particle in space. For example, at a detector, a phase shift might be due to a different origin point (creation point) or to a Bohm-Aharonov type phase shift. Quantum mechanics does not seem to focus on classical trajectories, but on spatial frequencies and their phase shifts and on interference between these.

We argue that certain potential (e.g. bound potentials, two slit potentials) etc may form a statistical resonance or equilibrium with a quantum particle i.e. with $\exp(ipx)$ which leads to a wave like result either in a bound state $W^*(x)W(x)$ or on a screen. It is possible, however, to destroy such an equilibrium. For example, one may place detectors behind each slit of a two slit system which destroy the equilibrium created sending the particle back into its initial state of a classical-like particle moving in space with fixed p . This does not seem so much like a collapse of a wavefunction than a dismantling of an equilibrium situation.

We also argue that it is possible to detect partial wave / partial particle information. For example, given a bound single particle system $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, one may knock out a particle. It should appear like a particle (not a wave) with a momentum p , but if one has an ensemble, one may determine $a(p)a(p)$ which provides some information about wave features of the system.

References

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